

EMPOWERING WOMEN IN LOCAL LEGISLATION: A COMPARISON ON THE ORDINANCES AUTHORED BY MALE AND FEMALE CITY COUNCILORS

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ABSTRACT

Women have been denied many rights throughout history that are fundamental to human dignity. Gender equality and true democracy are fundamentally dependent on women's political engagement. This research compares the ordinances that male and female councilors in the Philippines have authored. Using a qualitative narrative design, a semi-structured in-depth interview was conducted to understand women's political participation at the local legislative level. It also examines whether policies that support women's participation in society have become more common and whether gender directly influences policy decisions. The results of the research showed that there is no discernible connection between the number of female council members and their capacity to ratify ordinances. Even though they were a minority in the legislative council, female councilors were able to lead many committees and pass a number of ordinances. Furthermore, even though they are underrepresented, female councilors believe they are just as competent as their male counterparts despite having distinct approaches to legislative work. The findings of this study underscore the need for increased discourse regarding the gendered power dynamics within legislative processes. Additionally, it recommends that the local government work diligently to make it possible for more women to participate in active citizenship and run for office. This will give them more access to the legislative process and help the community become more accepting of people of different sexual orientations and pass more ordinances that will benefit all facets of the community.

Keywords: *gender equality, women's political participation, councilors, policy decision, ordinance*

INTRODUCTION

As politics continues to grow and change, it is becoming more and more clear that having a strong sense of self is essential to gaining influence. For the sake of enabling people to relate to their governing authorities, all classes and genders are now permitted to run for office, a change from ancient times when only men and the affluent could do so. Owing to this reality, scholars have developed research ranging from the direct effects of citizen participation in politics to identity politics, encompassing class, race, sex, and gender. Alporha (2022) examined the political dynamics of the women's suffrage campaign in 1937, while Swers (2001) centered on the significance of citizens' involvement in policy-making through the legislators they selected. Even if some of this research may be repetitive or overlap, they nevertheless succeeded in defining these phenomena, which will ultimately provide a greater comprehension of how a politician's identity may make or break their chances of winning public office for its constituents.

According to the most recent UN Women (2023) report on political involvement, women only make up 34% of local government seats on average across 136 nations. Berevoescu et al. (2021) claims that women are underrepresented in decision-making at all levels. This kind of data allows academics to fully understand the differences between the sexes' capacities for leadership and political engagement. Because of this, the research conducted by Firmalo-Fabric (2016) revealed that men dominate politics and that the Philippines' condition is similar to that of the UN research conducted (Alporha et.al, 2017).

While being a woman is not a prerequisite for addressing gender-specific issues, Swers (2001) discussed in her essay that while political figures will often speak up on matters affecting women, they rarely take part in debates to advance the establishment of gender equity. The main cause of this predicament is a lack of complete policy commitment, as seen by the incapacity to draft a set of backup plans when electing officials who are supportive of gender concerns (Pande, 1999).

Throughout the brief period of the Philippines' young democratic government, out of the 17 presidents since 1899, two of them were women and hailed from well-known political and business families. Women in the Philippines gained the right to vote in 1936, and since then at the present day, they have not only voted but have also entered their own candidacies for legislative positions and local government council positions in order to advocate for issues pertaining to the welfare of women (Aguilar, 1990). The Philippines is still a developing nation, and it seems that women's participation in local government elective roles is falling behind representation by barely making up less than 25% of the total population nationwide (Alporha, et.al, 2017).

Despite being a Catholic and conservative society, the Philippines has achieved enormous progress toward gender equality as stated by Republic Act No. 9710 which uphold women's rights and attempt to include their concerns into national growth. In addition, Republic Act No. 7192 was developed to support women's equal access to

opportunities and their capacity to make significant contributions. There are still many obstacles in the way of women seeking to be elected to political office, even in spite of these legislation. According to Valente and Moreno (2014), the aforementioned policies indicate that women will likely gain political influence in the future; nevertheless, this does not imply that men and women receive the same share of resources. Statista Research Development (n.d) provides an illustration to support this statement, indicating that the percentage of women holding parliamentary seats from 2014 to 2023 falls between 22% and 27.33% demonstrating that there is underrepresentation of women in the national legislative body even when taking into account both houses of Congress. Prior research that was conducted regarding women states that there still appears to be a power imbalance when it comes to the number of women who can be elected to political office, according to research done by women in politics who have concentrated on the significance of representing women at the national and international levels.

Regarding influence and female representation in politics, it is critical to recognize that the majority of women who succeed in breaking into the field do so because they hail from powerful families who made it possible for them to be given this chance. Similar to the initial phases of the Western feminist movement, particularly the first wave that centered on giving white women more chances to vote in the 19th century (Hooks, 1984). As stated by Hooks (1984) in her book, the original wave of feminism was founded on exclusive problems and sprang from the need for affluent women to demand more.

Despite the criticism, it developed into a legitimate worry that attracted public attention and propelled into the political movement that is today known as feminism. Western feminism has evolved into waves over time, with the second wave emphasizing systemic sexism and admitting that race plays a role in a woman's challenges (Friedan, 1963). Finally opening the door for the third wave, which disapproved of sexism at its core and identified it as the primary cause of sexual harassment in the workplace and public (Crenshaw, 1991 and Grady, 2018). Amidst the global expansion of Western feminism, Philippine feminism has made significant strides since women were granted the right to vote in 1936, paving the way for them to occupy political positions following colonization. But it was not without difficulty, since several lawmakers at the time thought that women's suffrage was not one of the urgent problems that needed to be resolved in order for all citizens, regardless of gender, to enjoy their freedom following the nation's independence from colonizers (Alporha, 2022).

Scholarly work such as this facilitates candid conversations on how, in cases of unequal political representation, initiatives that could address issues pertaining to women are sometimes marginalized. Frug (1992) clarified how male domination might be asserted through the lens of postmodern legal feminism through language used in legal discussions and may ultimately be converted into legislation. Aguilar (1990) concentrated her research on the historical overview of women's political participation across time, despite the fact that many studies address the impact of having women in politics. Conversely, Chattopadhyay and Duflo (2014) assessed the impact of required female presence in leadership roles with an emphasis on Indian legislation. Analyzing the effect of local legislation on fostering an egalitarian society for all people, regardless of sex, appears to be lacking in research.

This research seeks to provide an extensive analysis on the perceived relationship between gender and policy preferences in a more localized examination of local governments, albeit this may not be the same for every level of government. The researcher narrowed down the scope of the research to focus only on women's political participation at the local legislative level to enable them to thoroughly investigate whether or not gender directly influences policy decisions and whether or not policies that encourage women's participation in society have become more prevalent. Though several researches have already been conducted on women's political participation, very few, if any, have focused exclusively on the connection between gender and policy decisions made by local governments (Valente et al., 2014). By examining the ordinances passed by the elected city councilors, the research aims to offer a comprehensive discussion on the notable gender differences among local legislators and establish if power disparity exists in local legislation which they have authored.

Research Questions

1. Is there a difference between the laws authored by male and female councilors?
2. Do city councilors advocate for all sectors involved regardless of gender?
3. Are the laws authored by female councilors actually pave the way for equality between men and women in society?
4. How significant are the changes in the city brought about by women-authored ordinances?
5. Why is it important to have female representation in the local legislative process?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Since the primary focus of this research is to know the differences in policies enacted by city councilors, the researcher used a qualitative approach to gather insights and formulate a coherent interpretation in the most humanistic manner possible in answering the research questions. A qualitative approach enables the researcher to investigate and comprehend individuals, communities, and their cultural setting. In order to further do this, the researcher employed a narrative research design, which is advantageous for the topic as it addresses the justification of individual thought processes and provides structure for conceptualizing human experiences. According to Liamputtong (2009), narrative research gives participants from many industries a chance to share their experiences outside of the researcher's predetermined questions. A narrative research design will assist readers in comprehending the connection between the gender of the city councilor and their ability to influence local ordinance passage through their statements, as this research compares the ordinances authored by male and female councilors. Despite the fact that the number of participants in this research is smaller than that of previous research in the same sector, the researcher believes that a narrative approach to research can highlight important concerns and provide a detailed account of the legislators' extensive experience on the ground.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The most competent participants that can answer the research questions are the city councilors who were elected between 2013 and 2021. The criteria for the participants includes the following such as they had to be elected and declared as city councilors in the city of San Pedro, Laguna, in 2013, 2016, and 2019. They also had to have served the required term, which is three years for Filipino local legislators. In addition, the participants must agree to take part in the research that will allow the researcher to create a thorough comparison of the two genders and the reasoning behind the ordinances that each of them produced while serving as a city councilor throughout their tenure.

Since the primary goal of this research is to compare the ordinances authored and adopted by San Pedro city councilors who are male and female, certain criteria were used to choose the participants. Purposive sampling according to Ames et al. (2019) is applicable for research involving participants with similar qualifications in a variety of situations. The researcher were able to get information from the participants who are thought to have relevant knowledge on the topic of the research by employing purposive sampling technique.

Data Gathering Procedures

In order to conduct an in-depth interview, the researcher requested permission in writing from the intended participants, who are the city councilors. A consent form outlining the purpose of the research and providing reassurances regarding participant anonymity was provided to the participants following their approval.

In addition, to create a thorough analysis of the topic, the researcher employed semi-structured interviews with San Pedro, Laguna's city councilors elected between 2013 and 2021. Experts in the field of Political Science evaluated, approved, and validated the interview guide questions. Through the Sanggunian Panlungsod Secretariat, the researcher were able to get the ordinances of the elected councilors for the years 2013–2021 needed for the content analysis.

Data Analysis

The researcher utilized a content analysis on the city ordinances and a thematic analysis of the transcribed interviews using the information they had obtained from the collection of documents and in-depth interviews. The transcribed interviews were subjected to coding for a thorough analysis, which was covered in more detail. The interviews were classified in a preliminary manner according to contextual definitions, similarity of answers, and gender. Ordinances, however, used systematic content analysis. The researcher found that the approach of systematic content analysis will be best suitable when discussing the topic of identifying notable differences between male and female legislators' authored legislation. According to Brook (2021), in order to do a systematic content analysis of legal text, the researcher chose the legal text and its analysis parameters, in this case, city ordinances passed between 2013 and 2021. The next stage after choosing the source material was to start coding using the theoretical framework, which assisted the researcher in deciding on its codebook in advance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Similarities and Differences of Authored Ordinance

Every year before the start of the local legislative session, an ordinance is introduced to establish the Sangguniang Panglungsod's organizational framework. This facilitates the formation of committees and the election of committee chairs. The body may decide to add committees that could promote city growth or are particularly important to their citizens every three years following the election. Thirty mandatory standing committees with eleven elected city councilors have been established by the city of San Pedro since its rebuilding and cityhood.

In the city of San Pedro, two of the eleven elective seats are typically held by women. The fact that women are more frequently assigned to committees dealing with women and youth is not surprising. Because of this, female participants were able to advocate for industries such as youth and sports development, women and gender equality, consumer protection, health and sanitation, labor and employment, and by writing and enacting ordinances that aim to address any disagreement, resistance, or disruptions to one's comfortable way of life.

One of the male participants in the interviews stated that, "*ang mga babae ay mas nakakatulong sa pagpapa-ganda at pagpapa-unlad ng isang bayan,*" arguing that this is because women are naturally more nurturing than men, and as a result, they are more likely to create laws that protect people's general well-being. Conversely, the research discovered that more ordinances pertaining to ways and means, barangay affairs, budget, accounts, finance, and appropriation had been produced by men. Considering Hooks' (2000) analysis of the ways in which society shapes each gender in distinct ways, which will consequently influence how individuals depict their jobs in the sector of their choosing. This was made clear by the results of the research, which linked each gender's familial duties in their individual households to the policy decisions they are most inclined to prioritize. The research does, however, also wish to highlight and acknowledge the ordinances such as environmental protection and climate change, justice and human rights, public safety, prohibited drugs, peace and order, and laws and ordinances that both genders are more inclined to work on.

The researcher have also examined the justification for each ordinance in light of the findings reported in the section of this work that came before it. The typical justification for policies on justice and human rights is focused with the "prevention of discrimination and discouragement from unfair treatment," starting with the same and jointly prepared ordinances of male and female councilors. It comes as no surprise, then, that in the midst of a city's restructuring, the legislative branch supports the enactment of rules that will enable the community to more effectively navigate the developmental phases of its transition.

Following a similar line of reasoning, ordinances pertaining to public safety, prohibited drugs, and peace and order are co-authored by male and female councilors. The population of a certain geographic area is a necessary condition for reorganizing from a municipality into a city, and when that population grows, it makes sense to enact laws

that prioritize the value of every human life. The average number of co-authored ordinances by male and female councilors for each legislative year covered by this research has been almost six, with the justification being "to maintain peace and order by enacting measures to prevent and suppress lawlessness, disorder, riot, violence, rebellion or sedition".

Reorganizations require regulations to be followed in order to guide the organization's progress toward sustainability, just like in any other setting or organization. In order to address it, the male and female councilors of San Pedro co-authored and sponsored resolutions on laws and ordinances, which typically include amendments to previous city legislation "in support and consonance... changes are enacted within said ordinance to conform to the new standards of the city,". In keeping with the discussion, San Pedro's development into a competitive metropolis through infrastructure and the commercialization of previous residential areas may be hampered by environmental effects. Finally, to avoid more harm from 28 laws covering the years 2013–2021 were approved by the Committee on Environment Protection and Climate Change. These ordinances included provisions and justifications for San Pedro's continued growth as an urban community while maintaining the preservation of the area's natural areas.

Dominance in Creating Legislation

Frug (1992) discusses in Postmodern Legal Feminism how the law is often designed to make life easier for men because the world is inherently geared toward them. While this research cannot definitively establish it, dominance is evident in the way that male local politicians are backed when ordinances are being passed. The number of male councilors in San Pedro is addressed in this research, and the researcher explains here how it directly affects the number of ordinances they can pass and co-author in each legislative council. It has been stated that male participants have supported in areas including public works, utilities, infrastructure, livelihood and cooperatives, land use, transportation, housing and urban development, and public works resulted in 82 laws from various male councilors, many of which are sponsored by their fellow males. In the meantime, it is often documented that female councilors' ordinances were sponsored or co-authored by other female councilors. The researcher also noted during the interview the ideological variances among councilors who were the same sex. Four of the eleven male participants think that having female councilors is essential for the city particularly in the present era when they are better equipped to listen to the issues raised by underrepresented groups. The remaining male participants contend that because men are more visible on the streets and hence perceived as friendly, people feel more at ease contacting them than their female counterparts. Seven female participants were asked the same question and also had varying opinions about how important it was for women to hold elected office. Some claim that people oppose them because they are perceived as weak, but others think that their ability to sympathize with people makes them an excellent asset, resulting in their ordinances having personal feelings and the general improvement of a sector.

Cultural Representation

Local ordinances are passed after several hearings and then brought before the legislature for revisions and interpellation, much as how bills are passed into law at the

national level. In order to create these ordinances, city councilors must first consult their citizens, asking them to serve as resource people and listen to their needs for the well-being of the community. In the course of interviewing both male and female councilors for this research, the researcher found out the reason why these individuals typically succeed is not because of their ancestry, but rather because they merely "have the heart to serve the greater good" (Vergara, 2019). The researcher explains in this subsection how each councilor's representation can have a direct impact on the ordinances that are passed and implemented for the community that they affect.

Stereotypes generally come up when participants are asked what the biggest obstacle is for women trying to go into local politics. The female participants' response to the researcher's questions about these stereotypes during the interview was to "*equip myself every time I enter a session so that I do not have any question left unanswered*". Even though San Pedro has grown into an urban area, there are still underprivileged areas of the community that are frequently ignored. In-depth interviews with participants have revealed that, while male participants are aware of these sectors, their female counterparts typically follow up on this question by addressing ordinances that they have previously created or creating for those who were re-elected this legislative council to offer consolation and stigmatization in their daily lives.

According to a paper published by Mazad (2020), the author asserts that deeply embedded preconceptions continue to characterize attitudes toward female candidates, and opponents of politics frequently exploit these assumptions to cast doubt on the qualifications of women. The author also claims that there is still a stigma associated with women in politics and that these hurdles are structural, social, institutional, and cultural.

Conclusions

The value of a decision-making body's ability to supervise all sectors under its jurisdiction can be gauged by the proportion of female legislators in a rising city. Posts in local government are not usually as respected as those in national or provincial. But as the research went on, the researchers found that there is no clear relationship between the proportion of female councilors and their ability to approve ordinances. Despite being a minority in every legislative council, female councilors managed to enact 158 ordinances in various committees between 2013 and 2021.

Regarding if the influence of a man and a woman differs in each ordinance that they propose being passed. Participants who identified as women were asked about whether they thought women's issues and priorities differed from men's, if having more women in local government would have an impact, and what they had done while serving in that capacity. The participants' replies make it abundantly evident that women think they matter to local government and are just as capable as males, even though they approach legislative work in different ways. It is evident that male councilors do not obstruct the passage of sex discrimination laws written by women, despite having differing opinions on policies.

Recommendations

The researcher would like to recommend that sessions of interpellation and periods of amendments may also be collected to provide an exhaustive discussion on the power dynamics of gender in the legislative processes. In addition, the local government must exert a great deal of effort to enable more women to run for office or engage in active citizenship, which would increase their access to the legislative process so that the community will become more accepting of individuals with diverse sexual orientations, and more ordinances will be passed that will benefit all segments of the community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers declared that ethical standards were followed in the conduct of this research. Prior to their involvement, all participants gave their informed consent and were made aware of their freedom to discontinue participation at any moment without facing any repercussions. Throughout the course of the research, participants' confidentiality and identities were rigorously protected. The research was conducted without any conflicts of interest. Every source was correctly referenced. The results were used exclusively for research, and the analysis of the findings was carried out impartially.

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REFERENCES

- Aguilar, C. (1990). Women in politics in the Philippines. *Philippine Political Science Journal*. 6(31-32), 39–74. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/01154451.1990.975416](https://doi.org/10.1080/01154451.1990.975416)
- Alporha, V.C., Evangelista, M.S., and Hega, M.D. (2017). Feminism and the women's movement in the Philippines: Struggles, Advances, and Challenges. Friedrich Ebert Stiftung. <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/philippinen/14072.pdf>
- Alporha, V. C. (2022). Manuel L. Quezon and the Filipino women's suffrage movement of 1937. *Plaridel*. 19(1), 115-141. <https://doi.org/10.52518/2021-08valpor>
- Ames, H., Glenton, C. and Lewin, S. (2019). Purposive sampling in a qualitative evidence synthesis: a worked example from a synthesis on parental perceptions of vaccination communication. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 19(26). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-019-0665-4>
- Berevoescu, I., & Ballington, J. (2021). Women's representation in local government: A global analysis. Governance and Participation Section of UN Women. <https://www.unwomen.org/sites/default/files/2022-01/Womens-representation-in-local-government-en.pdf>
- Brook, O. (2021). Politics of Coding: On Systematic Content Analysis of Legal Text. In M. Bartl, P. Cebulak & J. Lawrence (Eds.). *Behind the Method: The Politics of European Legal Research*. 109-124. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3887536

- Chattopadhyay, R., & Duflo, E. (2004). Women as Policy Makers: Evidence from a Randomized Policy Experiment in India. *Econometrica*. 72(5), 1409–1443.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/3598894>
- Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Color. *Stanford Law Review*, 43(6), 1241–1299.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>
- Firmalo-Fabic, T. (2016). Women in Politics and Governance In Manang at Ading: A National Dialogue on the Past, Present and Future of the Women's Movement in the Philippines
- Friedan, B. (1963). *The feminine mystique*. Dell
- Frug, M. J. (1992). *Postmodern legal feminism*. Routledge: Taylor and Francis Group
- Grady, C. (2018) The waves of feminism, and why people keep fighting over them, explained. *Vox*. <https://www.vox.com/2018/3/20/16955588/feminism-waves-explained-first-second-thirdfourth>
- Hooks, B. (1984). *Feminist theory: From margin to center*. South End Press.
- Liamputtong, P. (2009). *Qualitative research methods*. Oxford University Press.
<http://ezproxy.deakin.edu.au/login url=>
- Mazad, S. (2020 March 13). The struggle for women in politics continues.
<https://www.undp.org/blog/struggle-women-politics-continue>
- Pande, R. (1999). Minority Representation and Policy Choices: The Significance of Legislator Identity. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1126985>
- Statista Research Development (n.d). Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments in the Philippines from 2014 to 2023.
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/730298/the-philippines-proportion-of-seats-held-by-women-in-national-parliament/>
- Swers, M. (2001). Understanding the Policy Impact of Electing Women: Evidence from Research on Congress and State Legislatures. *Political Science and Politics*. 34(2), 217–220. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1350206>
- UN Women (2022). *Regular Resources Report 2022: Accelerating Gender Equality*.
<https://www.unwomen.org/sites/default/files/2023-09/regular-resources-report-2022-en.pdf>
- Valente, J., and Moreno, F. (2014, August 15). Women's Representation in Local Politics: Evidence from the Philippines. National Food Authority, Philippines, Alliance for International Education. https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/57903/1/MPRA_paper_57903.pdf
- Vergara, P. (2019). Agueda Kahabagan was our first woman general. But do you know her? *Scout Magazine*. <http://www.scoutmag.ph/>